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1.0	2025.09.25	Mari Kleemola (TAU-FSD), Henna Kaartinen (TAU-FSD)	Internal comments incorporated, ready for publication

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TERMINOLOGY

Term/Acronym	Description
A F	Activities and Function
EDEN project	https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us
EC	European Commission
EOSC	The European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FIDELIS Network	https://eden-fidelis.eu/fidelis-network-tdrs
FIDELIS project	https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us
LoRCAP	Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation
TDR	Trustworthy Digital Repository
TF	Task Force
TTRAM	Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) aims to develop a web of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services for science in Europe. The FIDELIS project will enhance the sustainability of EOSC by establishing a network of trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs). The Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) has been designed to better understand repositories, and how transparency around the broad range of activities and functions they undertake can contribute to trustworthiness.

TTRAM has been developed in an iterative process through background research, sharing initial versions for feedback, and finalizing TTRAM based on the feedback. The Matrix is composed of 30 rows representing common repository activities/functions (A|F), a column for related transparent information, and two columns for repository variables.

Community feedback, flexibility and iteration continue to be key factors in the development of the TTRAM. However, the TTRAM Activities and Functions can be considered stable. The relationship between organisational characteristics and object characteristics is an important one for FIDELIS to address in the future.

Further work will include improving the TTRAM and launching pilot training. Collaboration with the EDEN project will ensure alignment with Core Preservation Processes. TTRAM will provide foundation for future FIDELIS work, including a tiered approach to capability and maturity of repositories, and for recommendations and guidance. Over time, FIDELIS will validate and publish mappings between the A|F and existing criteria, with considerations for principles, such as FAIR, CARE and TRUST.

The authors wish to thank everyone who has provided comments, and welcome further feedback, questions or comments about TTRAM via fidelis.matrixfeedback-request@postit.csc.fi.

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2. Introduction

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹ aims to develop a web of FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data and services for science in Europe. The FIDELIS project² will enhance the sustainability of EOSC by establishing a network of trustworthy digital repositories (TDRs). Within its three-year lifetime, FIDELIS will foster harmonisation and interoperability across repositories, contribute to upskilling of repositories, and provide a framework to support repositories in becoming and remaining trustworthy and FAIR-enabling over time.

Different trustworthy digital repositories preserving digital objects are key stakeholders for the FIDELIS project, the emerging FIDELIS Network³ and for the EOSC. The Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) has been designed to better understand repositories, and how transparency around the broad range of activities and functions they undertake can contribute to trustworthiness. In addition to providing a reference for the FIDELIS project and the Network, the TTRAM is a tool to support the EOSC EDEN project⁴ as well as the wider EOSC stakeholders in:

- Collecting information in a logical, reusable way
- Understanding the wide variety of types and practices across repositories
- Sharing structured information for consultation and use
- Designing and implementing a functional network of mutual support and aligned practice.

The goal is to reach a shared consensus on what constitutes a TDR in the context of EOSC.

The FIDELIS project tasks are divided into thirteen Work Packages (WPs) that are grouped into five Pillars (Fig. 1). The TTRAM has been developed in Pillar 3 by WP5 and can be used in WP2 for the Network membership model, in Pillar 4 for developing the training and support offers, and in Pillar 5 for communications and outreach. The TTRAM will provide the foundation for WP6 (Year 2) that will form a tiered approach to capability and maturity of repositories and explore solutions that enable repositories to prepare for federation, and for recommendations and guidance (WP7 Year 3).

This milestone report describes the process of creating the *FIDELIS M12 First version of TTRAM*, provides an overview of the TTRAM, and outlines the next steps.

¹ European Open Science Cloud (EOSC): <https://eosc.eu/>

² FIDELIS project: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us>

³ FIDELIS Network: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/fidelis-network-tdrs>

⁴ EDEN project: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/about-us>

	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Pillar 1 (CSC)	Project Management (WP1)		
Pillar 2 (Sikt)	Preparing and initiating the network (WP2)	Consolidating the network and value-add (WP3)	Transition the network and value-add (WP4)
Pillar 3 (TAU-FSD+ Skit)	Building common understanding of TDRs and a harmonized matrix of repository capabilities and characteristics (WP5)		Recommendations and guidance (WP7)
Pillar 4 (DANS)	Repository training and support:	Initiating network cohesion and support (WP8)	Strengthening the network (WP9) Consolidating the network (WP10)
Pillar 5 (Trust-IT)	Strategic alliance, cascading grants, communication and dissemination (WP11-13)		

Figure 1. FIDELIS Pillars and Work Packages

3. TTRAM development

The TTRAM has been developed by FIDELIS WP5, more specifically by Task 5.1 *Tiered definitions, concepts, characteristics and criteria of TDRs*. The development of TTRAM has been an iterative process. It has included background research, collecting feedback on draft versions, and finalizing the TTRAM v1.0 based on the feedback received, source materials and the FIDELIS landscape analysis⁵.

3.1. Background and source materials

The TTRAM has a wide range of dependencies and interdependencies. These include, but are not limited to, the FIDELIS project and the Network, EDEN project, EOSC Federation, EOSC Association Task Forces (esp. TF Retention), repository certification bodies, EC, Horizon Europe and the Annotated Model Grant Agreement. This implied that the Matrix should cover a broad range of activities and functions that are influenced by a range of variables that impact the characteristics of repositories, registries and the digital objects’ data, and metadata that they care for. The TTRAM seeks to support alignment rather than replace current work. Reference source materials are presented in Appendix: Sources Used to Define the Activities & Functions.

3.2. Iterative process informed by community feedback

The TTRAM development process has followed an iterative approach, with community feedback systematically integrated to inform and guide enhancements. Feedback has been collected from the FIDELIS WP5 team, all FIDELIS project partners, the EDEN project, and from a wider group of stakeholders. The main steps are described below.

⁵ Jouneau, T., Verburg, M., Horton, L., van Geest, G., Tujunen, S., Kallio, J., Paulsen, T., Duvaud, S., Recker, J., Holthe-Tveit, Å. J., Thorpe, D. E., Conzett, P., Kleemola, M., Kalaitzi, V., Huber, R., Jonquet, C., Aguilar, F., Forshaug, A. K., Alaterä, T. J., & Esteves, E. (2025). FIDELIS landscape survey analysis (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15744996>

In January - March 2025, the Task 5.1 team developed the first draft of the TTRAM.

In April 2025, the first draft was shared for feedback. A webinar to introduce the TTRAM was held on April 4th⁶. The main target groups were the FIDELIS and EDEN project teams although the webinar was open to anyone to attend. Feedback period lasted until the end of April and the community was asked to: 1) add comments in the introduction and overview document; 2) add comments to the design statement; and 3) copy the Matrix template spreadsheet and fill it from their own repository's viewpoint. The last task was asked especially from the FIDELIS WP5 partners, who were also offered two virtual Ask-Me-Anything support sessions on 29.4. and 15.5.2025.

In May 2025, the Task 5.1 team revised the TTRAM based on the community feedback.

In June 2025, the second draft was shared. The FIDELIS project and TTRAM work were presented in the IASSIST conference⁷ in Bristol, United Kingdom. The 2nd virtual FIDELIS TTRAM webinar⁸ on June 17th introduced the model to a wider audience and was attended by 60+ participants. Feedback was collected during the webinar, by sharing a google document, and via email. The feedback period lasted until 15.8.2025 and the community was asked to:

- Identify gaps and need for clarifications in the activities and functions (A|F) and their descriptions
- Provide good examples of documents or metadata related to A|F that their organisation provides or uses
- Identify gaps and need for clarification on the Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation
- Comment on any additional object, depositor or user characteristics that would help understand repository types
- Comment alignments between the Matrix and existing standards and criteria, and give suggestions for future alignment
- Identify any related areas of focus the FIDELIS Network should take forward, e.g. events, activities or user groups.

In August - September 2025, the Task 5.1 team finalised the TTRAM version 1 (see ch. 4).

The WP5 team would like to thank everyone who has provided comments, feedback or other input during the TTRAM development process. Overall, the amount of interest and feedback exceeded the expectations. The key points of the feedback can be summarised followingly:

- 1) Requests to improve clarity and the goals of TTRAM (e.g. definitions of terms, sources, should all template cells be filled in, level of transparency)
- 2) Suggestions to improve the structure of the TTRAM (e.g. diagrams)
- 3) Comments on the repository variables (e.g. requests to add more examples)

⁶ 1st TTRAM Matrix Webinar: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/events/introduction-ttram-matrix-webinar>

⁷ Kleemola, M., Alaterä, T. J., & Verburg, M. (2025, June 4). FIDELIS: Uniting the European digital data repository community beyond finite project efforts. IASSIST 2025, Bristol, UK. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15642284>

⁸ 2nd TTRAM Matrix Webinar: <https://eden-fidelis.eu/events/introduction-ttram-matrix-webinar-0>

The number of the filled-in matrices is currently eleven. They have been used to improve the TTRAM and in developing a training pilot related to TTRAM (by FIDELIS WP8), and will be used as a basis for further FIDELIS work in 2026-2027.

The feedback also informed the FIDELIS project’s response to the CoreTrustSeal Requirements revision⁹.

3.3. Validation of Levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP)

The level of care digital objects receive from a repository may differ significantly not only between repositories but also between digital objects in a repository. Repositories must inform their users and other stakeholders clearly the level of curation and preservation delivered for each digital object in their holdings. The level can influence what information is made transparent. Therefore each TTRAM activity or function is considered against the levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) provided by the repository.

The TTRAM uses the levels of care produced through a CoreTrustSeal community consultation¹⁰. They have been endorsed by the EOSC Long Term Data Preservation Task Force¹¹ and referenced by the EOSC Retention Task Force¹². During the TTRAM process and when collecting CoreTrustSeal Requirements revision feedback from the FIDELIS partners, no feedback contradicted the LoRCAP model, which we interpret as further supporting its validity.

Figure 2. The levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)

⁹ CoreTrustSeal Trustworthy Data Repository Requirements Review 2026-2028: <https://www.coretrustseal.org/why-certification/meeting-community-needs/trustworthy-data-repository-requirements-review-2026-2028/>

¹⁰ CoreTrustSeal Standards and Certification Board. (2024). Curation & Preservation Levels: CoreTrustSeal Position Paper. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11476980>

¹¹ EOSC Long Term Data Preservation Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-preservation/>

¹² EOSC Retention Task Force <https://eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/>

The levels of retention, curation and appraisal are (see Fig 2.):

- Z. Level Zero. Retention-only. Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access. Data content and supporting metadata are stored for a given time period.
- D. Deposit Compliance. Data content and supporting metadata deposited are checked for compliance with defined criteria.
- C. Initial Curation. The digital objects are curated by the repository to meet defined criteria.
- A. Active preservation. Long-term responsibility for ensuring that the data and metadata can be understood and rendered as required by the designated community for reuse.

4. Overview of the TTRAM

The Matrix is composed of 30 rows representing common repository activities/functions, a column for related transparent information, and two columns for repository variables.

4.1. TTRAM documents

The FIDELIS Transparent, Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix (TTRAM) is a simple Matrix Template supported by a brief Guide, an Introduction and Overview, and a Design Statement. They are available on Zenodo:

- FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Introduction and Overview (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144159>
- FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Guide (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144141>
- FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Template (v01.00). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144259>
- FIDELIS TTRAMatrix v01.00 Design Statement v01.00. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17144178>

We encourage readers to start with the Introduction and Overview. The Guide includes detailed guidance and examples on how TTRAM can be deployed, populated and expanded. The template is a spreadsheet that provides space to add information relevant to each A|F. The Design Statement describes the drivers behind the design of the TTRAM.

4.2. Structure of the TTRAM

The TTRAM is composed of:

- 30 rows representing common repository activities/functions
- a column for related transparent information
- two columns of repository variables:
 - Levels of Retention, Curation and Preservation (LoRCAP)
 - Depositors, Users and Objects covered by different repositories

4.3. Activities & Functions

The TTRAM Activities and Functions (Table 1) are divided into five groups: context, digital object management, organisational infrastructure, technology and security. The Activities and Functions (A|F) are based on a range of existing standards, criteria and requirements (see Appendix).

Table 1. TTRAM Activities and Functions

Context Identification & Contact Mission & Scope	Organisational Infrastructure Governance Policy & Standards Rights Resources	Technology Storage & Integrity Technical Infrastructure
Digital Object Management Conceive, Create, Collect Deposit & Appraisal Curation, Quality & Compliance Discovery & Identification Access ReUse Workflows Preservation	People & Expertise Third Party Dependencies Continuity of Service External Engagement Release & Publishing Interoperability Legal & Ethical Criteria, Assessment, Improvement Analysis & Impact Training Research & Development	Security Security

The TTRAM Guide provides a detailed description of each A|F and a visualisation of the relationships between them. The TTRAM Template includes examples and suggestions that can be included, amended or deleted as necessary.

4.4. Transparent Information

Transparency of information is a dependency for mutual understanding, cooperation and support. The TTRAM suggests and collects information about repository practices. The template provides space for adding titles, descriptions and links to information artefacts (policies, procedures, references, standards, legislation etc), and metadata relevant to the A|F. Figure 3 presents an example of what kind of transparent information the repository may make available.

Transparency does not necessarily imply that information must always be public. The degree of transparency required depends on the context.

Transparent Information
<p>Documentation of compliance criteria applied at the point of deposits, whether automated or manually applied and the degree to which they are required or optional.</p> <p>Collections Development and Appraisal Policy</p> <p>Deposit Compliance Criteria</p> <p>Deposit Procedures</p> <p>Deposit Licence</p> <p>Acceptable/Preferred File Formats List</p>

Figure 3. Example of transparent information in the TTRAM

4.5. Variables

In TTRAM, each Activity or Function is considered against local repository *Variables*. Together, the activities, functions and local variables are used to propose related information (including policies, standards and procedures) that could usefully be made transparent. The current variables included in the TTRAM are:

- the levels of retention, curation and preservation (LoRCAP) provided by the repository
- the characteristics of the repository's digital objects, depositors and users

Together the activities/functions and contextual variables help repositories identify what information should be made transparent.

Variables	
Levels of Retention, Curation & Preservation (LoRCAP)	Repository Depositors, Users and Objects (Included / Excluded)
<p>LoRCAP: maps to Deposit Criteria. Depending on the LoRCAP deposit of an object may be permitted or restricted based on suitability for initial curation or active preservation.</p>	<p>Institutional repositories may limit depositors to one or more specific organisations. National repositories may require that research or a researcher is based in a specific country or that the digital object is relevant to users in a specific nation. Specialist repositories may permit or restrict objects based on their disciplinary relevance, supporting metadata, content types or funders.</p>

Figure 4. Variables in the TTRAM

5. Conclusions and next steps

The key conclusions are:

- Community feedback, flexibility and iteration are key factors in the development of the TTRAM. Additional variables will be incorporated based on feedback and analysis of the evolving landscape.
- The TTRAM Activities and Functions can be considered stable. The TTRAM will support alignment and cooperation in the Network, across EOSC and beyond.
- A single repository may offer multiple levels of care with different levels for different digital objects. This relationship between organisational characteristics and object characteristics is an important one for FIDELIS to address.
- This milestone achievement indicates that the project is progressing as planned, with no need for adjustments or reorganization.

The next steps in **October - December 2025** include further feedback collection, improving the TTRAM and writing of *Deliverable 5.1 Harmonised Matrix of Repository Functions, Activities & Characteristics* due in December 2025. In addition, WP5 team will collaborate with the EDEN project to align TTRAM with the Core Preservation Processes¹³ developed by EDEN. FIDELIS WP8 will launch pilot training for repositories to utilize TTRAM. Existing and newly developed FIDELIS training resources will be classified and categorised using the TTRAM to support their discovery, use and maintenance. The TTRAM will also provide a foundation for FIDELIS WP6 (in 2026) that will form a tiered approach to capability and maturity of repositories and explore solutions that enable repositories to prepare for federation, and for recommendations and guidance in 2027 (WP7).

Over time FIDELIS will validate and publish mappings between the A|F and existing criteria to support Network members in managing alignment with different expectations. This will require planning for how outputs (e.g. crosswalks) should be presented, versioned and maintained for maximum usability to a broader audience. In addition, the Matrix will cover additional variables; for example including how repositories can enable the FAIR, CARE and TRUST Principles.

The FIDELIS WP5 team would like to thank everyone who has provided comments, feedback or other input, and welcomes further feedback, questions or comments about TTRAM via fidelis.matrixfeedback-request@postit.csc.fi.

¹³ EOSC EDEN T1.2, Lindlar, M., Caron, B., Benauer, M., Kylander, J., Dekeyser, K., Addis, M., Levlin, M., Laukkanen, M., Lehtonen, J., Burger, F., Koho, T., Schwab, F., Molloy, L., & Zhang, F. (2025). M1.1 Report on Identification of Core Preservation Processes. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16992452>

Appendix: Sources Used to Define the Activities & Functions

Source	URL
1. CoreTrustSeal. (2022). <i>Trustworthy Digital Repositories Requirements 2023-2025 Extended Guidance. (V01.00)</i> . Zenodo.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7051096
2. L'Hours, H., Recker, J., & Kleemola, M. (2023). <i>CoreTrustSeal+FAIRenabling: Alignment between the FAIR Principles and CoreTrustSeal 2023–25 (01.00)</i> . Zenodo.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7564703
3. Wilkinson, M., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. <i>Sci Data</i> 3, 160018.	https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18
4. Subcommittee on Open Science of the National Science and Technology Council. (2022). <i>Desirable characteristics of data repositories for federally funded research</i> . Executive Office of the President of the United States.	https://hdl.handle.net/10088/113528
5. National Institutes of Health. (2020). <i>Supplemental Information to the NIH Policy for Data Management and Sharing: Selecting a Repository for Data Resulting from NIH-Supported Research</i> .	https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-21-016.html
6. Confederation of Open Access Repositories. (2022). <i>COAR Community Framework for Good Practices in Repositories, Version 2 (Version 2)</i> . Zenodo	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7108101
7. Ramezani, S., Aalto, T., Gruenpeter, M., Herterich, P., Hooft, R., & Koers, H. (2021). <i>D2.7 Framework for assessing FAIR Services (V1.0)</i> . Zenodo.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656431
8. National Digital Stewardship Alliance. (NDSA). (2019). <i>Levels of Preservation (Version 2.0)</i> .	https://ndsa.org//publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/
9. Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D. et. al. (2020). <i>The TRUST Principles for digital repositories</i> . <i>Scientific Data</i> , 7, Article 144.	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7
10. Durinx, C., McEntyre, J., Appel, R., Apweiler, R., Barlow, M., Blomberg, N., et al.. (2017). <i>Identifying ELIXIR Core Data Resources, version 2</i> . <i>F1000Research</i> , 5(ELIXIR), 242.	https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.9656.2
11. Digital Preservation Coalition. (2021). <i>Rapid Assessment Model (DPC RAM), Version 2</i> .	https://www.dpconline.org/docs/miscellaneous/our-work/dpc-ram/2005-dpc-ram-worksheet
12. Digital Library Federation. (DLF). (2020). <i>Levels of Born-Digital Access. OSF</i> .	https://osf.io/hqmy4